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Appraisal of the Adoption and Occupant's Satisfaction of Modular Expanded Polystyrene Buildings in Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study adopted a convergent parallel mixed methods design to examine the factors militating against the adoption and occupant satisfaction with modular expanded polystyrene housing in Abuja, Nigeria. Two manufacturers were interviewed while questionnaire survey was administered on 144 respondents sampled from a population of 503. The data from the interview were subjected to thematic analysis to identify the factors militating against the adoption of modular EPS, while data from the survey were subjected to mean ranking to assess the satisfaction levels of the occupants of EPS buildings. The findings revealed that technological factors, particularly relative advantage, compatibility, and sustainability, account for 58% of the cited factors, while organisational factors such as internal capabilities, production processes and cost-effectiveness contribute 18.4%. Environmental factors account for 14.7%, while human factors on the other hand make up 8.1% of the total factors militating against the adoption of modular EPS housing. The study also shows that occupant's satisfaction with the modular EPS buildings is overall high in the study area. The study concludes that adoption of modular EPS housing in Abuja is driven primarily by its technological qualities (relative advantage, compatibility, and sustainability), while occupants' satisfaction with the modular EPS buildings is overall high. The study recommends technical standardization developing Nigerian EPS panel standards for durability and fire performance. It also recommended infrastructure support for modular EPS factories to enhance reliable power provision such as solar power backup grants and enhancement of fire safety systems, improvement of interior aesthetics and exterior finishes to push overall satisfaction even higher.

Keywords: Adoption, EPS buildings, Modular housing, Occupant's satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's exploding population and urbanisation pressures have resulted a staggering housing deficit, currently estimated at over 21 million units (World Bank, 2018). Conventional housing construction methods which are laborious, slow, and expensive are ill-equipped to meet this deficit. As a response, attention is now being focused on alternative construction technologies such as Modular Expanded Polystyrene (EPS), which promises affordability, speed, thermal comfort, and design flexibility (Dave, Watson & Prasad, 2017; Ngugi *et al.*, 2017). Despite the proven benefits and global success of modular building systems, uptake in Nigeria remains limited.

Modular construction can be categorized as a Modern Method of Construction (MMC) or offsite construction industry system, also known as volumetric construction (Musa *et al.*, 2015). Modular

construction is a modern and holistic approach to building construction which carried out in the following phases: pre-design phase, design phase, features, order, fabrication, delivery and final assembly (Sholanke *et al.*, 2019; Smith, 2016).

Modular construction essentially connotes three common activities, i.e., production of precast components at a factory, delivering the precast components to the construction site and assembling the precast components to form buildings (Xue, Zhang, Su & Wu, 2017). The decreased tasks essential for the fabrication process leads to less waste, reduced likelihoods of the incidence of inaccuracies and rework. These are the ultimate principals that assures some extent of customisation while retaining the standards of productivity, cost and quality of bulk manufacture (Da Rocha, Formoso and Tzortzopoulos, 2015).

The comparative advantages of modular construction are in the increasingly little differentiation between the conventional building types and the “componentized” and the “panelized” prefabrication types. In this context, the differentiation is made by checking the proportion of the prefabrication components relative to the onsite manufactured components. On this basis, a building is classified as a modular building where the prefabricated component is more than 50% of the total building value, or vice versa (Shahzad *et al.*, 2015). Their lightweight nature reduces foundation requirements, while closed-cell foam provides high thermal insulation and sound dampening (Mesaros, Spisakova, Kyjakova & Mandicak, 2015; Ngugi, Kaluli & Abiero-Gariy, 2017). Studies in India and Kenya establish 30 to 40% cutbacks in construction time and 20 to 30% energy saving above conventional masonry (Ansari, Singh & Jain, 2022; Boafu, Kim & Kim, 2016). The adoption of modular housing is usually influenced by the requests of the client for faster completion of construction, greater quality, increased economy of scale and chance for single point procurement (Cambridge Centre for Housing and Planning Research, 2021).

Modular Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) brings a pre-manufactured technology into the development of reinforced concrete buildings. This system involves production of panels of curly/undulated form of polystyrene from the refining procedure of crude oil. The panels are enclosed on each side with electro welded zinc coated wire mesh forming a three-dimensional reinforcement steel. To build walls, the panels are covered with a layer of shotcrete using a pneumatic system. A single panel allows the construction of a building up to four floors while double panels can take up to fifteen floors (Ngugi *et al.*, 2017). The prefabricated expanded polystyrene panel is a self-supporting structure that improves the thermal insulation of walls. It facilitates transportation, loading, unloading and linking individual components into a structure because it is a material with low specific gravity. Foam polystyrene is a heat-insulating material that has very low thermal conductivity, eradicates heat leakage bridges and does not require timber in the roof structure (Mesaros, Spisakova, Kyjakova & Mandicak, 2015).

The implementation process of innovation such as modular construction consists of five levels - initiation level, followed by adoption, adaptation, acceptance, re-utilisation (Zhu, Dong, Xu & Kraemer, 2006) and infusion as the additional level according to (Tambovcevs & Merkurjev, 2009). After the initiation level for creating awareness about new technology, the level of adoption, which is blended into three stages, will be performed. The three steps of the adoption level are the intention to adopt, actual adoption, and innovated technology (Kim & Crowston, 2011). With the awareness of the housing industry stakeholders on specific innovation or new technology, certain factors influencing actual adoption should be investigated. Therefore, identifying the real and potential factors influencing modular housing implementation is important and provides greater confidence in the decision to integrate modular construction more effectively by stakeholders in the Nigerian housing industry. The decision-making process of selecting one construction method over another is usually motivated by the specific site conditions, availability of skilled labor, transportation conditions, organizational readiness, local codes, project schedule and budget, sustainability requirements and design complexity (Azhar, Ahmad & Lukkad, 2013). Accordingly, Mahbub (2015) submitted that jobsite accessibility, the number of storeys of the structure, affordability of the finished housing, overall time of construction, quality and accuracy in construction are instrumental in deciding to adopt modular construction systems. Other researchers relate the decision to adopt modular construction systems to its comparative advantages over other construction methods, such as its unique ability to be disassembled and reassembled while still maintaining asset

value, construction time saving-since site preparation and manufacturing process of the modules can occur simultaneously (Akok & Prakask, 2017). These results in early return on capital investment, avoidance of disruption and loss of operation of adjacent buildings, pre-compliance trials are easily carried out off site and off the critical construction path and earlier building occupancy (Kamali & Hewage, 2017).

In Nigeria, Kolo *et al.* (2014) highlighted reluctance to innovate, paucity of codes and standards, high capital cost, supply chain integrations, insufficient guidance and information and skill requirements as the core challenges to the adoption of offsite manufacturing. Some of the issues associated with modular construction systems bothers on the requirement for expensive hauling and cranes for handling large prefab components (Modular Building Institute, as cited in Shahzad *et al.*, 2015) and the long time required for advanced ordering (Shahzad *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, Shahzad and Mbachu (2012) identified the requirement for “personalised designs with the flexibility for alterations to suite lifestyle preferences in the design and construction phases is limited in the system. Another obstacle impacting prospective developers, is the little incentive to be gained in refining and using innovative technologies, since primarily value is placed on the land assets rather than techniques of construction (Mahbub, 2015). Accordingly, Wuni and Shen (2020) synthesized the five most impactful challenges to the adoption and diffusion of modular housing systems to include “industry, knowledge, process, financial and technical challenges”. An all-inclusive view is that the adoption of modular housing systems is determined by four variables: technology, organization, environment and human. These variables are composed of measurable factors. Complexity, relative advantage, compatibility, waste reduction, sustainability, perceived ease of use, weather window and quality of product are regarded as Technological factors. Manufacturing process, technical barrier, cost of construction, cost of transportation and construction time are organizational factors that are specific to the firm or company. The industry, local codes and site conditions are environmental factors affecting the adoption of modular housing systems. The human factor on the other hand has to do with the availability or absence of skilled labour needed to adopt modular housing systems. A firm or company’s analysis of these variables determines their attitude towards the use of the technology and subsequent decision to adopt it or not (Hadi, Omar, Sheik Osman & Hussaini, 2020).

According to Dave, Watson and Prasad (2017) The performance and perception in modular housing are products of ‘environmental sustainability’ and ‘economic affordability’. The environmental sustainability characteristics include operating energy efficiency from good thermal performance, that is, energy efficient fixtures, appliances and equipment; overall lifecycle; environmental considerations; waste and resource minimization strategies; water efficient fixtures, appliances and equipment; and environmentally preferable materials. While the economic affordability characteristics comprises of cost effective materials, cost-effective designs; initial purchase (up-front) cost, cost of operation, and maintenance cost. A building performance tool that has been extensively used to evaluate the performance of buildings and assessing the satisfaction of the users and owners, is the post-occupancy evaluation (POE). The features usually evaluated include user’s assessment of building comfort and function, user’s satisfaction, and user’s behavior (Wongbumru & Dewancker, 2016). A post-occupant evaluation can be conducted by means of the Building User Satisfaction (BUS) survey, ‘Housing Evaluation’. “Housing Evaluation usually comprises background, the residence overall, indoor conditions and personal control, lifestyle and utility costs (Woo, 2017). The indicators for post-occupancy evaluation to include quality of design, quality of building support services and indoor environment quality. The quality of design comprises the quality of all architectural features of a building, like the interior appearance, exterior appearance, building layout, and facilities. The indoor environment quality consists of indoor air quality, acoustic comfort, thermal comfort, security, fire safety and visual comfort. The quality of building support services comprises of availability and quality of water supply, quality of water closets and washrooms, laundry, electricity, information technology. These facilities ought to be suitably designed, correctly installed and be easy to maintain for the use standards of the building (Mustafa, 2017).

Earlier studies in Nigerian addressed the technical merits and broad adoption barriers of on modular buildings (Kolo, Rahimian & Goulding, 2014) and architects’ level of awareness regarding the adoption

of modular construction system in Nigeria (Sholanke, Opoko, Onakoya, and Adigun, 2019), but none integrated manufacturers' operational insights with residents' perspectives to assess the uptake of modular EPS buildings. Similarly, while Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theories have been applied in appraising housing innovations internationally (Davis *et al.*, 1989; Rogers, 1962), their application to EPS housing in an African setting is yet to be explored. This study fills that gap by combining qualitative and quantitative data to explore the factors militating against the adoption and occupant satisfaction of modular EPS buildings within Abuja's housing ecosystem, addressing why a potentially transformative innovation is slow to scale. Specifically, this will be achieved through by identifying the factors that facilitate or impede EPS deployment in the study area and assessing the occupant's satisfaction levels with the functional efficiency of modular expanded polystyrene buildings in the study area.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a convergent parallel mixed method designed to examine the factors and prospects associated with the adoption of modular expanded polystyrene buildings for housing delivery in Abuja. The population of the study was the summation of the 4 senior engineers and production managers from two major Abuja EPS manufacturers (CITEC and PIL) for the qualitative aspect, while 503 occupiers of the modular buildings at CITEC and PIL EPS housing estates constituted the population of the quantitative phase. In this design qualitative and quantitative data collection occurs concurrently. The data were then analysed independently, and then merged. Collecting both quantitative and qualitative data helped to achieve complementarity through elaboration, enhancement, illustration and clarification of the results from one approach with the other.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 4 senior engineers and production managers from two major Abuja EPS manufacturers (CITEC and PIL). Discussions explored production workflows, quality control, cost structures, and organisational capabilities.

Structured questionnaire anchored on Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) constructs were administered on 144 residents living in EPS housing estates. Respondents rated 20 items on a five-point Likert scale covering perceived advantage, compatibility, complexity, sustainability, process efficiency, and institutional support. Cronbach's alpha for the full scale was 0.90.

Questionnaire Administration

One hundred and forty-nine questionnaires were administered and one hundred and thirty-nine with 93% response rate were collected through google forms. The one hundred and thirty-nine (139) questionnaires were used in running the analyses.

Table 1: Questionnaire Administration

Questionnaires	Number	Response rate (%)
Administered	149	100
Collected	139	93
Screened	139	93%

Source: Field Survey (2021)

Data Integration and Analysis

Qualitative data from the interviews were coded using thematic analysis into technological, organisational, environmental and human categories. The number of times each theme was mentioned in the interviews were given quantitative scores. The scores were then analysed descriptively, and drivers/barriers were ranked by frequency and mean importance.

FINDINGS

Factors Militating Against the Adoption of Modular EPS Housing

After reading through the transcript multiple times, each paragraph was coded with one or several of the initial code categories depending on the theme of the paragraph. As the goal of the analysis was to search for themes that occur across the datasets from the two companies in relation to their conception of the

factors militating against the adoption of modular housing, the first step after coding was to compare the frequency of the factors identified in the two document groups by using the quantitative Compare Cases & Groups feature. This feature created a crosstab that allows for both a quantitative and also visual interpretation of the technology, organization, environment and human factors that determine adoption as opined by Hadi *et al.* (2020). This is presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Factors Militating Against the Adoption of Modular EPS Housing

S/N	Factors	Sub-factors	CITEC	PIL	Total	Percentage (%)	
1.	Technology	Relative advantage	9	19	28	20.6	
2.		Complexity	1	3	4	2.9	
3.		Compatibility	4	13	17	12.5	
4.		Sustainability	11	2	13	9.6	58.8%
5.		Perceived ease of use	2	3	5	3.7	
6.		Quality and efficiency of product	5	4	9	6.6	
7.		Prospects of modular polystyrene	1	3	4	2.9	
8.	Organization	Manufacturing process	6	4	10	7.4	
9.		Technical barrier	3	1	4	2.9	
10.		Cost of construction	1	4	5	3.7	18.4%
11.		Transportation challenges	1	1	2	1.5	
12.		Construction time	0	4	4	2.9	
13.	Environment	Industry	2	2	4	2.9	
14.		Local codes	3	3	6	4.4	
15.		Site condition	1	1	2	1.5	14.7%
16.		Electricity	0	3	3	2.2	
17.		Standard of Construction materials	1	4	5	3.7	
18.	Human	Skilled labour	1	3	4	2.9	
19.		Corruption	2	0	2	1.5	8.1%
20.		Resistance by Professionals	3	2	5	3.7	
SUM			57	79	136	100	
N = Documents			1	1	2	100	

Source: Field Survey (2021)

Table 2 above shows the frequency distributions from the code groups representing the factors militating against the adoption of modular housing. The frequencies represent the number of times that particular sub-factors were mentioned or identified in the respective interviews conducted in the study areas. Twenty sub-themes were identified under the four factors militating against the adoption of modular housing in the study areas.

Technological factors

Manufacturers identified relative advantage (percentage = 20.6) and compatibility with local construction practices (percentage = 12.5) as the strongest technological drivers. Perceived sustainability (percentage = 9.6) and quality and efficiency (percentage = 6.6) also scored highly. Complexity and concerns about panel durability in extreme weather conditions were the primary technological barriers (percentage = 2.9). In all, technological factors accounted for 58.8% of reported adoption drivers and barriers, underscoring the primacy of design attributes in user acceptance.

Organisational factors

Crucial organisational enablers included streamlined production processes (percentage = 7.4), cost-effectiveness compared to masonry (percentage = 3.7), and in-house quality control systems (M = 3.90). Barriers centred on technical barriers and construction time (percentage = 2.9) and transportation

challenges (percentage = 1.5). Organisational factors explained the remaining 18.4% of adoption dynamics.

Environmental factors

The key environmental factors are the availability or absence of local codes on modular housing (percentage = 4.4), standard of EPS construction materials (percentage = 3.7). While the lesser factors are underdeveloped industry (percentage = 2.9), inadequate electricity (percentage = 2.2) and site condition (percentage = 1.5). Environmental factors are among the important considerations in the sustainable adoption of modular EPS housing and account for 14.7% of adoption dynamics.

Human drivers and barriers

Human factors include resistance by professionals (percentage = 3.7), lack of skilled labour (percentage = 2.9) and corruption (percentage = 1.5). The human factors make up 8.1% of the total factors militating against the adoption of modular EPS housing.

Integrative insights via TAM and DOI

Mapping these results onto TAM and DOI reveals that perceived usefulness (relative advantage, sustainability) and ease of use (compatibility, streamlined processes) drive positive intention to adopt, while complexity and weak organisational support dampen diffusion—aligning with Davis et al. (1989) and Rogers (1962).

Summary of factors militating against the adoption of EPS housing

Conclusively, the study finds out that technological qualities and organizational factors are the most influential factors mitigating against the adoption of modular EPS housing.

Occupant’s Satisfaction Levels with the Functional Efficiency of EPS Buildings

Table 3: Satisfaction Levels with the Functional Efficiency of EPS Buildings

Building Attributes/Services	Std.			Criteria
	Mean	Deviation	Ranking	
Strength and stability	4.44	.852	1	Satisfied
Height Adequacy	4.35	.634	2	Satisfied
Thermal Comfort in dry season	4.30	.461	3	Satisfied
Walls	4.29	.607	4	Satisfied
Floors	4.27	.600	6	Satisfied
Accessibility	4.25	.817	5	Satisfied
Thermal Comfort in rainy season	4.24	.427	7	Satisfied
Structural safety	4.24	.505	8	Satisfied
Redundancy	4.21	.747	9	Satisfied
Quality of building materials	4.17	.533	10	Satisfied
Lighting, air quality, acoustic and temperature	4.16	.725	11	Satisfied
Electrical safety	4.09	.379	12	Satisfied
Maintenance	4.04	.570	13	Satisfied
Security in the building	4.02	.503	14	Satisfied
Choice of location	3.87	.337	15	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Fire safety	3.76	.813	16	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Quality of interior	3.67	.736	17	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Grouping	3.63	.934	18	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Exterior appearance	3.49	.674	19	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Comparative cost of EPS	3.35	1.165	20	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied

Source: Field survey, 2021

Summary of occupant satisfaction findings

Table 3 shows the level of occupants’ satisfaction with the functional efficiency of modular buildings at CITEC and PIL. It evaluated 20 attributes based on five-point measurement scale. Out of 20 evaluated attributes, 14 fall into the “Satisfied” category and 6 into “Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied.” This distribution reveals a generally high level of approval for the functional efficiency of modular buildings in the study area.

Breakdown and pattern of satisfied attributes

Top satisfaction attributes (Mean ≥ 4.24)

Figure 1: Showing Satisfaction Attributes with ranging from 4.24 and above.

Moderate satisfaction attributes (Mean 4.02–4.24)

These 14 attributes demonstrate that residents feel confident in both the structural integrity and day-to-day usability of their modular spaces.

Figure 2: Showing Satisfaction attributes with Means from 4.02 to 4.24.

Neutral satisfaction attributes

The six attributes with Means between 3.35 and 3.87 suggest areas of ambivalence:

Figure 3: Chart showing Satisfaction attributes with Means between 3.35 to 3.87.

DISCUSSION

Factors Militating Against the Adoption of Modular EPS Housing

The study findings demonstrate that technological factors are the most influential factors accounting for 58.8%. This is in agreement with Wuni and Shen (2020), Harvey (2016) and Musa *et al.* (2015), whose study identified technological qualities as one of the factors affecting the diffusion of modular construction in the housing industry. This shows that the technological factors are the most important considerations of the modular EPS manufacturers.

Factors that have to do with the Organization, that is the modular manufacturers internal capabilities are the second most important group of factors with a percentage of 18.4%. This suggests that in spite of how promising a technological innovation is, the capacity of the organization intending to adopt it plays an important role in determining the success of the adoption of such a technology. This finding is comparable with the previous findings of Wuni and Shen (2020). Environmental factors are the next most important considerations in the sustainable adoption of modular EPS housing. Environmental factors account for 14.7%. These factors are influential because they are external factors which the organization usually have limited or no control of, which have impact on the adoption of the modular EPS technology. This finding concurs with the findings of Harvey (2016).

Human factors make up 8.1% of the total factors militating against the adoption of modular EPS housing. This finding is indicative of the fact that regardless of how good an innovation is, the availability of skilled labour and the attitude of people who use such an innovation has the potential to determine the successful adoption or failure of the innovation. This finding is in agreement with Harvey (2016) and Musa *et al.* (2015). This demonstrates that technological attributes of EPS like its insulation performance, speed of assembly, and adaptability are essential but not adequate for widespread adoption. Organisational readiness, specifically workforce skills, stable infrastructure, and quality management equally play crucial roles, resonating with Musa *et al.* (2015). In Abuja, manufacturers have improved production workflows but are constrained by reliable power and shortages of skilled labour.

Comparatively, modular EPS systems in Europe and Asia supplement strong technology with robust vocational programs and supportive policy incentives, ensuring a skilled labour pipeline and predictable factory operations (Kamali & Hewage, 2017; Zohourian, Pamidimukkala, Kermanshachi & Almaskati, 2025).

Satisfaction Levels with the Functional Efficiency of EPS Buildings

Residents overwhelmingly rate the modular buildings as functionally efficient, especially in structural strength, spatial design, and thermal performance. These findings are consistent with studies by Woo (2017), Mustafa (2017), and Wongbumru & Dewancker (2016), this research confirms high occupant

satisfaction with prefabricated building functionality. The study however, diverges from Dave, Watson & Prasad (2017) because that work focused on operational energy efficiency and lifecycle environmental impact, whereas the current study centres on user-perceived comfort, safety, and material quality.

CONCLUSION

Adoption of modular EPS housing in Abuja is driven primarily by its technological qualities (relative advantage, compatibility, and sustainability), while organisational factors (cost-effectiveness and process efficiency) further enhance uptake. Barriers in organisational readiness (power supply, workforce skills, and training) are critical hurdles. Incorporating TAM and DOI viewpoints highlights that scaling EPS housing requires coordinated enhancement of technology qualities, institutional support, human component and environmental characteristics. Furthermore, the occupant's satisfaction with the modular EPS buildings is overall high, highlighting its potential for wider adoption to bridge the existing housing deficit in Abuja, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance the uptake of modular EPS housing the study recommends:

1. Nigeria's nascent modular sector must pursue parallel investments in both innovation design and organisational capacity to realize EPS's full potential.
2. Technical standardization by developing Nigerian EPS panel standards for durability and fire performance.
3. Partnering with technical institutes to introduce modular construction modules and EPS fabrication capacity building training.
4. Infrastructure support for modular EPS factories to enhance reliable power provision such as solar power backup grants.
5. Housing policy realignment to include EPS systems in building codes and offer tax incentives for industrialised housing projects.
6. Sponsor public-sector EPS housing trials to showcase performance and build stakeholder confidence.
7. To push overall satisfaction even higher, stakeholders should target enhancement of fire safety systems, improvement of interior aesthetics and exterior finishes.
8. Addressing perceptions around EPS cost and optimizing building layout.

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